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Report on the literature search and climate suitability analysis of *Retithrips syriacus* (Mayet, 1890)

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Abstract

Climate suitability analysis allows to identify regions where climate is likely to support the establishment of a pest. This analysis is typically based on pest ecophysiology and/or distribution according to the different methodology/models available. In the context of the related EFSA pest risk assessment, a systematic literature search and climate suitability analysis was performed for *Retithrips syriacus* (Mayet, 1890). The current report includes the result of the systematic literature search conducted to retrieve data and information available in the scientific literature, the description of the methodology, the results of the climate suitability analysis, and the list of the files published in the Zenodo including all the collected data: (i) an excel file including metadata on the literature analysed, (ii) an excel file including the observed distribution of the pest, (iii) maps related to the climate suitability analysis of *R. syriacus*, (iv) a Geopackage file including the layers related to the climate suitability analysis, and (v) a zip folder containing the QGIS styles used to build the maps.

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Keywords: (climate suitability, pest risk assessment, pest distribution, *Retithrips syriacus*, black vine thrips)

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1 Introduction

Climate suitability analysis allows risk assessors to identify regions where climate is likely to support the establishment of an organism (IPPC, 2013). This analysis is typically based on the biology and/or distribution of the organism according to the different methodology/models available (Devorshak, 2012). A systematic literature research, in accordance with EFSA systematic review methodology (EFSA, 2010), was performed to gather relevant information on the distribution, physiology, ecology, hosts, pest biology, control methods, pest spread, and/or impact of *Retithrips syriacus* (Mayet, 1890). The data extracted from the literature search were used to analyse the climate suitability of *R. syriacus* in the EU.

2 Note on this report

This document includes a description of the methodology and results of the systematic literature search and climate suitability analysis developed in the context of the EFSA Scientific Opinion on *R. syriacus* for the European Union (EFSA Plant Health Panel et al., 2024). For a complete discussion of results and conclusions of the present analysis, please refer to the related Scientific Opinion.

3 Methods

3.1 Systematic literature search

Literature search was performed to capture the existing literature on *R. syriacus*. The Web of Science (All Databases) and Scopus literature databases were queried, and search results were crosschecked (and integrated if needed) with records from EPPO Global database and CABI. Only the scientific and common names of the pest, retrieved from the EPPO GD¹, CABI², and CABI Thesaurus³ (Table 1) were used to develop the search string (Table 2). No other keywords were used (e.g., “biology”, “physiology”, “temperature”, “distribution”, etc...) not to limit the retrieval of documents useful for the purposes of this search.

Table 1. Scientific and common names, taxonomy, EPPO code, and main hosts of *Retithrips syriacus*.

Scientific name	<i>Retithrips syriacus</i> (Mayet, 1890)
Other scientific names	<i>Retithrips aegyptiaca</i> (Marchal) <i>Retithrips aegyptiacus</i> (Marchal) <i>Stylothrips bondari</i> (Bondar/ Morgan) <i>Dictyothrips zanoniana</i> (Del Guercio) <i>Heliothrips syriacus</i> (Mayet)
International common names	black vine thrips, castor thrips (English) tripes vermelho de maniçoba (Portuguese) thrips nero de la vid (Spanish)
Taxonomy	Kingdom: <i>Animalia</i>

¹ <https://gd.eppo.int/>

² <https://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/>

³ <https://www.cabi.org/cabithesaurus/mtwdk.exe?yi=home>

 Phylum: *Arthropoda*
 Subphylum: *Hexapoda*
 Class: *Insecta*
 Order: *Thysanoptera*
 Family: *Thripidae*
 Genus: *Retithrips*
 Species: *Retithrips syriacus*
 EPPO code
 RETTSY

Table 2. Search string queries and results from Web of Science and Scopus.

Platform	Date of search	Query	N of documents
Web of Science	06/02/2023	TS=("Retithrips syriacus" OR "Retithrips aegyptiaca" OR "Retithrips aegyptiacus" OR "Stylothrips bondari" OR "Dictyothrips zanoniana" OR "Heliothrips syriacus" OR "black vine thrips" OR "tripes vermelho de maniçoba" OR "thrips nero de la vid" OR "castor thrips")	109
Scopus	06/02/2023	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Retithrips syriacus" OR "Retithrips aegyptiaca" OR "Retithrips aegyptiacus" OR "Stylothrips bondari" OR "Dictyothrips zanoniana" OR "Heliothrips syriacus" OR "black vine thrips" OR "tripes vermelho de maniçoba" OR "thrips nero de la vid" OR "castor thrips")	12

All the references were exported to the reference manager software EndNoteX9 (The EndNote Team, 2013) and checked for duplicates.

3.2 Document screening and data extraction

Document screening was performed using the software DistillerSR (Evidence Partners, 2022) and followed a two-step approach: Title and Abstract (TIAB), and Full Text screening. In both steps the documents were screened answering the question "Is this reference relevant for the QPRA?". The first step was based on the title and abstract and the above question was applied to discriminate between relevant, irrelevant, and unclear references. A reference was considered relevant if it contained information on Pest Distribution, Physiology-Ecology, Hosts, Pest Biology, Control Methods, Pest Spread, and/or its Impact. By selecting the answer "Yes" (Figure 1), the reference was automatically moved to the next screening level (i.e., full text). When from the abstract it was unclear whether information of interest was available from the title and the abstract the "Unclear" option was selected, automatically carrying the paper on to the next step. The second step of the screening was based on the full text of the documents that passed the first step and an ad hoc questionnaire, divided in seven sections (Distribution, Physiology-Ecology, Hosts, Pest Biology, Control Methods, Spread, and Impact) was used to facilitate the extraction of data and information.

Reference Details

RefID: 2046, Occurrence of the black vine thrips, *Retithrips syriacus* Mayet, on avocado in Israel and trials to control the pest by insecticides of plant origin
Izhar, Y., Yehuda, B., Swirski, E., Wysoki, M., Dagan, M.

Actions ☰

Attachments
PDF - Izhar_1992.pdf (Standard Version) | (Annotatable Version)

Full Text Links
[DOI.org](#)

Reference Label(s):

In field tests in Israel, avocados cv. Horshim, 4102 and TX-531 were the most susceptible to *Retithrips syriacus*. Trials to control the pest with botanical insecticides showed that 2% extracts of *Sabadilla* [*Schoenocaulon officinale*] were more effective than 2% extracts of *Ryania*.

1. Is this reference relevant for the QPRA?

Figure 1. Title and Abstract Screening, Screenshot from DistillerSR (DistillerSR. Version 2.43. Evidence Partners; 2021. Accessed Jan-Sep 2023. <https://www.evidencepartners.com>).

Data extraction was also performed in DistillerSR for the documents passing the full-text screening.

Table 3: Information extracted from the documents and collected in the master file.

Field name	Description	Type
<i>Refid</i>	Record ID. The Refid number is a unique number associated to each reference in Distiller	Integer
<i>Reference</i>	Full reference for the record	String
<i>Source type</i>	Categorises the type of reference. Available options: original study, review study, distribution map, other	String
<i>Distribution</i>	Presence of information on distribution (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>Physiology_Ecology</i>	Presence of information on physiology and/or ecology (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>T</i>	Presence of information on temperature (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>RH</i>	Presence of information on humidity or moisture (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>Photoperiod</i>	Presence of information on photoperiod (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>Host</i>	Presence of information on host availability (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>Biology</i>	Presence of information on pest biology (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>Impact</i>	Presence of information on the impact of the pest (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>Spread</i>	Presence of information on the spread of the pest (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>Control Methods</i>	Presence of information on control methods used against the pest (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean

A Master File was developed containing a summary of the information contained in each reference. Seven independent tables on each of the topics relevant for the QPRA were developed: Pest Distribution, Host list, Pest Biology, Control Methods, Pest Spread, and Impact. Table 3 includes an explanation of the fields present in each of the independent tables.

3.3 Data analysis

3.3.1 Köppen–Geiger climate classification analysis

The SCAN-Clim tool (European Food Safety Authority & Maiorano, 2022) was used to develop climate suitability maps based on the climate classification approach. The Köppen–Geiger climate classification from Kottek et al. (2006) after the re-analysis of Rubel et al. (2017), based on the period 1986–2010 (available at <http://koeppen-geiger.vu-wien.ac.at/present.htm>), was used. The climate types present in the observed locations of *R. syriacus* were identified and mapped. Since the area of the assessment is the EU, the output maps considered only climate types that are also present in the EU. The Köppen–Geiger map was created using only point observations (identified through coordinates) as input presence data.

3.3.2 Weather data for the calculation of the climate indicators

The climate indicators used in this analysis (paragraphs 3.3.3 and 3.3.4), apart from the Köppen–Geiger climate classification, were calculated using the ERA5-Land dataset downloaded from the Copernicus Climate Data Store (Muñoz Sabater, 2019) for the period 1993–2022 on a global 0.1° x 0.1° grid.

3.3.3 Hardiness zones map

The hardiness zone map is a classification based on the average minimum annual temperature. It is an indicator which has been used extensively in relation to the geographic distribution of perennial plant species (Daly et al., 2012). However, this indicator can also be useful for inferring areas where a pest could overwinter or not based on winter temperatures.

The hardiness zones map implemented for this analysis was based on the updated version of the Agricultural Research Service USDA (2023), which identifies 13 main zones, each divided into two subzones, for a total of 26 hardiness zones.

The specific point locations where *R. syriacus* was observed (paragraph 4.2) were used to sample the average annual minimum temperature raster layer. The sampled minimum value was used as a threshold to identify the minimum hardiness zone where the pest was observed. All the grid cells having an equal or higher hardiness zone were mapped.

3.3.4 Maps with the average maximum number of consecutive days below the lower development threshold (LDT)

The average maximum number of consecutive days below the lower development threshold was used as an indicator of climate conditions particularly unfavourable to *R. syriacus*. The LTD was calculated as described in the related EFSA Scientific Opinion (EFSA Panel on Plant Health, 2024, paragraph 2.2.1.1. *Lower development threshold*). The specific point locations where *R. syriacus* was observed (paragraph 4.2) were used to sample the raster layer of this climate indicator. The sampled maximum value for this indicator was used as a threshold and all the grid cells having an equal or lower value were mapped.

3.3.5 Geoprocessing of climate indicators: union and intersection

Given the different EU areas identified by the three different climatic indicators (Köppen-Geiger, Hardiness zones, and the average maximum number of consecutive days below the lower development threshold), maps of the union and the intersection of the three maps based on the indicators were developed and considered as the potential minimum suitable area (the intersection map) and the potential maximum suitable area (the union map) scenarios.

3.3.6 Identification of suitable NUTS2 regions in the EU

The information at the grid level was summarized at NUTS2 level to identify the administrative units potentially suitable for establishment. The suitable NUTS2 regions were identified overlapping the union and intersection maps and, for each NUTS2, the percentage of area at risk of potential establishment was calculated.

4 Results

4.1 Systematic literature review

The PRISMA diagram (Moher et al., 2009) in Figure 2 summarizes the results of the systematic literature search. The search in Web of Science and Scopus gathered 109 and 12 documents, respectively. Eighteen additional references found in Google Scholar and other sources were added. A total number of 139 references were obtained. After deduplication in EndNote, 113 were imported to DistillerSR and underwent the TIAB screening. Of these, 37 references were excluded because they did not contain relevant information, and the remaining 76 were passed to the Full text screening. After the end of the TIAB screening, 13 additional papers were found and added. Data extraction was performed for 76 references as 13 were not relevant or a repetition of already collected information. Therefore, 63 references constituted the sources for the present analysis. In 62 of these records data on pest distribution was extracted, 68 contained details on the hosts, 14 about physio-ecology of the pest, 36 concerned its biology, 25 the impact, 11 the spread, and 24 the control methods.

Figure 2. PRISMA Diagram describing the process followed to identify, screen, and include eligible information on the distribution, hosts, physio-ecology, biology, impact, spread, and control methods for *R. syriacus*.

4.2 Observed pest distribution

The literature search yielded 189 records of observation at both point locations (coordinates) and administrative unit level (Figure 3). From the observed distribution, 46 are point locations, reporting specific coordinates indicated in the paper or taken from Google Earth⁴. The remaining

⁴ <https://earth.google.com/web/>

143 observations are administrative units (e.g., countries, regions) identified through their FAO Global Administrative Unit Layer (GAUL) codes⁵.

Administrative boundaries: © FAO-UN
Cartography: EFSA 02/2024

Figure 3. Known global distribution of *Retithrips syriacus* (data extracted from the systematic literature search performed by EFSA). Red dots represent point locations, grey areas are administrative units where the pest was reported.

4.3 Climate indicators

4.3.1 Köppen–Geiger climate types

Among the climate types present in the EU, *R. syriacus* was observed in the hot semi-arid (BSh) and Mediterranean hot summer (Csa) Köppen–Geiger climate types (Figure 4. Köppen–Geiger map for *Retithrips syriacus*). These climate types are widespread in the Mediterranean areas of the EU, and in Southern Portugal.

⁵ https://developers.google.com/earthengine/datasets/catalog/FAO_GAUL_2015_level1

Figure 4. Köppen–Geiger map for *Retithrips syriacus*.

4.3.2 Hardiness zones

As a result of the analysis, the hardiness zones from 10a to 13b were assumed as potentially suitable (Figure 5). These areas include mainly the south-west part of Andalusia (Spain) and Southern Portugal, Cyprus, Malta, Açores (PT), Madeira (PT), and the coastal areas of Spain, Southern France, Italy.

Figure 5. Hardiness zone map based on the average annual minimum temperature for the period 1993-2022. The map highlights the hardiness zones (highlighted in grey in the legend) in the EU where the average minimum temperature is higher or equal to the minimum value sampled using *R. syriacus* occurrences. The Hardiness zone map is based on the recent implementation of the USDA Plant Hardiness Zones (2023).

4.3.3 Average maximum number of consecutive days below the lower development threshold

The area in the EU including a value for this indicator equal or below the number sampled in the location of observations was restricted mainly to the South-West coastal areas of Andalucia (SP), Balearic Islands (SP), Cyprus, Malta, Madeira (PT), and some Greek islands.

Average maximum number of consecutive days with the minimum air temperature below 14.9 °C in the EU and neighbouring countries

Highlighted in red are areas with the average maximum number of consecutive days ≤ 114.83 days
 Climate data source: Muñoz Sabater, J., (2019) was downloaded from the Copernicus Climate Change Service (2022). The results contain modified Copernicus Climate Change Service information 2020. Neither the European Commission nor ECMWF is responsible for any use that may be made of the Copernicus information or data it contains.
 Administrative boundaries: © FAO-UN © Eurostat
 Cartography: EFSA 04/2024

Figure 6. Average maximum number of consecutive days below lower development threshold for the period 1993-2022. The map highlights the areas (in red) in EU where the average maximum number of consecutive days is equal or below the maximum value sampled using the *R. syriacus* distribution occurrences (section 3.3.4).

4.4 Union and Intersection of climate indicators

Figure 7 shows the result of the intersection and union of the three climate indicators considered for *R. syriacus*, representing the 'potentially minimum suitable area', and the 'potentially maximum suitable area', respectively. The union area was substantially larger than the intersection area. Considering the areas covered by the single climate indicators, the union area was mainly driven by the Köppen–Geiger climate types, while the intersection area mainly by the average maximum number of consecutive days below the lower development threshold.

Figure 7. Union (light green) and intersection (dark green) of Köppen–Geiger climate types, Hardiness zones, and average maximum number of consecutive days below the lower development threshold. For each indicator, only the areas relevant for *R. syriacus* were considered.

5 Content of the *Retithrips syriacus* Zenodo repository

Retithrips_syriacus_Climate_Suitability_Report.pdf

The file contains the methodology and results of the Climate Suitability Analysis for *R. syriacus*, describing the extensive literature search and the climate classification. The results of the databases interrogations are presented together with the process applied for documents screening and selection, summarised by a PRISMA diagram. Maps illustrate the pest distribution and the results of the climate suitability analyses. Although, we refer to the related PRA (EFSA Panel on Plant Health, 2024) for an exhaustive and detailed discussion of the results.

Retithrips_syriacus_ANNEX_A_Master_File.csv

The file contains the list of documents selected for data extraction. The description of the fields is in *Retithrips_syriacus_ClimateSuitability_Report.pdf*.

Retithrips_syriacus_ANNEX_B_Observation_File.csv

The file contains the observed distribution at a global level. Both point locations and administrative units are included.

Maps in .jpeg format

- *Retithrips_syriacus_Distribution.jpeg*
- *Retithrips_syriacus_KG.jpeg*
- *Retithrips_syriacus_areas_below_LDT.jpeg*
- *Retithrips_syriacus_Hardiness_zones.jpeg*
- *Retithrips_syriacus_Union_and_Intersection.jpeg*

Retithrips_syriacus.gpkg

GeoPackage (.gpkg) file containing the GIS layers of the results of the analysis.

Retithrips_syriacus_qgis_styles.zip

QGIS styles to replicate the symbology used in the maps published in the PRA. These styles were applied to the layers contained in *Retithrips_syriacus.gpkg*

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